
Economic Valuation of Wetland Ecosystem Services: Determinants of Local Residents' Willingness to Pay for Conservation in the Jakhor Lake Complex, Nepal

Govinda Raj Upadhyay¹, Ashutosh Priya², Dharma Dev Bhatta¹, Janak Raj Joshi³, and Gori Raj Kadayat³

¹ PhD Scholar (Economics), Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, UP, India, Department of Economics, Aishwarya Multiple Campus, Dhangadhi, Kailali, Nepal (Affiliated to Tribhuvan University)

² Professor, Department of Regional and Applied Economics
Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, UP, India

³ PhD Scholar (Economics), Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, UP, India, Far Western University (FWU) Department of Economics, Durga Laxmi Multiple Campus Attariya, Kailali, Nepal.

Abstract

Wetland ecosystems provide critical services, yet their conservation in developing regions remains underfunded and understudied. This study estimates residents' willingness to pay (WTP) for wetland conservation in Jhakhor Lake, Nepal, and identifies key socioeconomic and spatial determinants influencing valuation. Using face-to-face household surveys with 411 residents, contingent valuation method (CVM) and Tobit regression models were employed to analyze WTP and its drivers. Results indicate that 90.27% of respondents were willing to contribute financially, with a mean WTP of 249.20 NPR annually among positive responses. The distribution of WTP was highly right-skewed (Shapiro-Wilk $W = 0.388$, $p < 0.001$), with a median of 120 NPR, reflecting significant heterogeneity in valuation. Regression results revealed that education, income, and frequent visitation positively influenced WTP, whereas larger household size and greater distance from the wetland significantly reduced it. Spatial factors, particularly proximity to the lake, emerged as strong predictors, underscoring the role of use values and accessibility in shaping conservation preferences. These findings highlight the potential for community-financed conservation initiatives and provide an empirical basis for designing equitable payment for ecosystem service (PES) schemes. By incorporating spatial and socioeconomic heterogeneity into valuation models, this study offers policy-relevant insights for wetland management in Nepal and similar Himalayan contexts, where balancing ecological integrity and local livelihood needs remains a pressing challenge.

Keywords: *Willingness to pay, wetland conservation, contingent valuation, Tobit model, spatial determinants, Ecosystem services*

Introduction

Wetlands encompass marshes, fens, peatlands, and water bodies whether natural or man-made that may contain fresh, brackish, or saline water in either still or flowing form. The definition also extends to coastal and marine areas with a depth of no more than six meters at low tide (Thapa et al., 2022). Wetlands are highly adaptive ecosystems that provide essential services supporting the socio-economic well-being of surrounding communities. Their goods and services can be assessed through both quantitative and qualitative approaches, independent of direct market pricing. Such valuation, when compared with other economic sectors, offers critical insights that facilitate evidence-based planning, policy development, and decision-making (Tian et al., 2020; Upadhyay, 2022). The Ministry of Forests and Soil Conservation (MFSC, 2015) reports that wetlands in Nepal cover approximately 743,563 hectares, accounting for about 5% of the

country's total land area and supporting more than 20,000 waterfowl. Among these, eleven sites covering 60,561 hectares have been designated as wetlands of international importance (MoFE, 2018). Wetlands support the livelihoods of millions of people locally and globally by consistently delivering a wide range of ecosystem services (MoFE, 2018). These services arise from the diverse species and ecological processes within wetland habitats, which not only sustain biodiversity and life-support functions but also serve as indicators of how human activities influence the provision of ecosystem services (Sah & Heinen, 2001). The ecological environment serves as a fundamental prerequisite for human survival and socio-economic development. The rapid growth of the global economy, along with urbanization and industrialization, has put immense pressure on water resources, upsetting the natural balance of aquatic ecosystems. Recognizing this challenge, Nepal took a significant step in 2003 by launching a pilot eco-compensation project in the Kulekhani watershed Khatri (2011). This initiative provided incentives to upstream communities for forest conservation, with the dual purpose of safeguarding the environment and balancing the interests of those who rely on ecosystem services with those whose activities affect them. Such efforts emphasize that valuing and managing ecosystem services is vital not only for maintaining ecological integrity but also for sustaining the well-being and livelihoods of dependent communities. Liu and Yang, (2012) studied in china and fund that eco-compensation is viewed as a system that uses economic tools to improve ecosystem services while ensuring a fairer distribution of benefits among different. Over time, it has gained recognition not only as an environmental policy but also as a political tool that helps regulate and support the responsible use of natural resources (Thieme et al., 2012). The concept of eco-compensation closely supports with the idea of Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES), though certain distinctions remain (Adhikari et al., 2017). Ecosystem services (ES) are the benefits derived from natural systems and the species within them, which sustain human life and livelihoods (Jo et al., 2021). PES is typically defined as a voluntary arrangement in which beneficiaries of ecosystem services compensate providers to ensure their continued supply (Chen et al., 2020). Such mechanisms operate on the principle of voluntary beneficiary payment (Bamwesigye et al., 2020) are often guided by market dynamics, and promote ecological protection through incentive-based activities. In contrast, eco-compensation is largely government-led, founded on the "polluter pays" and "beneficiary pays" principles. It relies primarily on fiscal transfers to internalize the externalities of ecological degradation and to encourage conservation through targeted economic incentives (Geng et al., 2023). Thus both PES and eco-compensation serve as effective mechanisms for promoting ecological conservation and sustaining ecosystem balance.

Eco-compensation has been widely studied in environmental research and is increasingly applied in practice. Ecosystem services in the Jakhor Lake wetland are dynamic, with some generated locally and others originating from outside Dhangadhi, both of which influence the sustainable development of Jakhor Lake (Upadhyay, 2022). Most studies have focused on valuing ecosystem services in individual wetlands, such as Jagadishpur, Ghodaghodi, Bedkot, and Rani Lakes, often overlooking the interactions between upstream and downstream areas. Research on eco-compensation in trans-regional wetland areas remains limited. Globally, approaches to eco-compensation for natural lakes differ due to variations in theoretical frameworks, technical capacities, national policies, and cultural contexts (Wang et al., 2019). In Nepal, eco-compensation for natural lakes is still in its early stages, and developing standards for trans-regional compensation continues to be a major challenge for policymakers.

The determination of an eco-compensation standard for Jakhor Lake is closely linked to the effectiveness of its conservation. Currently, methods such as the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) (Halkos et al., 2020). The opportunity cost approach (Acharya et al., 2021), and choice experiments (Hagedoorn et al., 2020) are commonly applied to estimate eco-compensation standards for wetland ecosystems. The Contingent

Valuation Method (CVM) is a widely used stated preference technique that assesses individuals' willingness to pay (WTP) or willingness to accept (WTA) compensation for environmental goods and services by simulating a hypothetical market scenario (Tian et al., 2020; Makwinja et al., 2022). It has been extensively employed to estimate values for environmental resources, renewable energy initiatives (Bimonte et al., 2020) and a range of environmental protection projects (Chu et al., 2020). Eco-compensation standards for a Jakhor lake can be calculated using either Willingness to Pay (WTP) or Willingness to Accept (WTA), which represent economic value and socio-ecological perspectives, respectively, rather than relying solely on the total value of ecosystem services. Horowitz and McConnell (2003), these metrics are also effective for quantifying the change in value resulting from a change in the quality of the same environmental good. When faced with a decline in environmental utility, individuals may state the compensation they are willing to accept (WTA) to offset the welfare loss from this degradation (Feng et al., 2018). Conversely, they might indicate a sum they are willing to pay (WTP) to prevent such environmental deterioration from occurring (Peng et al., 2018). However, a well-documented phenomenon is that WTA valuations tend to be significantly higher than WTP for the same ecological good, a bias highlighted by (Peng et al., 2018).

Building on the theoretical foundation of WTP, Various empirical studies have sought to identify the key determinants that influence an individual's willingness to pay for environmental goods. These factors are generally categorized into attitudinal and socioeconomic dimensions. For instance, a respondent's level of environmental awareness is a significant positive predictor of WTP (Upadhyay, 2022). Furthermore, standard socioeconomic characteristics including age, gender, education, and income consistently emerge as critical variables. However, the direction and strength of their influence can vary. Some research indicates that age may correlate with diminished ecological awareness and lower WTP (Osiolo, 2017), while gender differences have been observed, with women sometimes expressing more certain WTP values than men (Osiolo, 2017), Higher levels of education and income are frequently associated with greater motivation for ecological protection and a correspondingly higher WTP (Upadhyay, 2022).

To analyze these relationships, researchers employ a variety of econometric models, such as Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, Logit models, Tobit models (Peng et al., 2018 Upadhyay et al. 2025). Despite this body of work, the findings across different contexts remain mixed, underscoring the need for context-specific studies to clarify the socioeconomic determinants of WTP for particular ecosystems like wetlands.

The establishment of effective eco-compensation mechanisms is a critical challenge in environmental management. While such mechanisms aim to balance ecological protection and economic benefits, their compensation standards are often contested. Ideally, these standards should be based on robust valuations of ecosystem service value (Peng et al., 2018). However, in practice, they are frequently determined by top-down governmental decisions rather than local ecological and social contexts Meng et al. (2019) leading to potential inefficiencies and a lack of local buy-in. This gap underscores the necessity of empirical, ground-level valuation studies to inform equitable and effective conservation funding. Assessing residents' willingness to pay (WTP) provides a direct, democratic method to establish a credible compensation standard that reflects the value local communities place on their natural assets, such as wetlands.

Therefore, to address this critical gap, the present study aims to evaluate residents' willingness to pay (WTP) for wetland conservation, identify its key socioeconomic determinants, and estimate the associated ecosystem service value for Jhakhor Lake in Nepal. The primary contributions of this research are threefold. First, it applies the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) through household surveys to quantitatively estimate the WTP of local residents, providing a foundational value for conservation initiatives. Second, it introduces

and analyzes contextually relevant variables, such as ethnicity and proximity to the lake, to deepen the understanding of factors influencing WTP in a Nepalese socio-ecological context. Finally, by employing a Tobit model calibrated with primary data collected directly from the community, the findings offer an authentic reflection of local preferences. This empirically grounded approach ensures that the results are robust and can inform tailored, effective, and locally acceptable wetland conservation policies.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted at Jhakhori Lake, a perennial oxbow wetland located in Dhangadhi-7, Dewariya, within the Kailali district of Nepal (28°70'641" N, 80°6225° E). As a significant biodiversity hotspot in the country's tropical lowlands (150 meters above sea level), the lake plays a vital role in regional ecological conservation. The main water body spans 13.49 hectares and is hydrologically connected to two smaller adjacent lakes, Murfutta (2.52 ha) and Murfutti (1.32 ha), located within 0.5 km. The wetland is characterized by its seasonal hydrology, relying primarily on rainfall and forest seepage. Water levels fluctuate considerably, with minima during the dry seasons (winter and summer) and maxima that often lead to overflow during the monsoon. The northwestern shore is bordered by dense forest, which connects to the extensive Dewariya Botanical Garden (149.50 ha) to the south.

The conservation of wetland ecosystems is critical for maintaining biodiversity and supporting local livelihoods, particularly in developing regions. Jhakhori Lake, a perennial oxbow wetland in the Kailali district of Nepal, exemplifies this importance. Its ecological richness, sustained by a unique interplay of aquatic and terrestrial habitats, provides essential resources for nearby communities. However, like many vital ecosystems worldwide, it faces the pressing challenge of balancing conservation needs with local economic development.

Globally, eco-compensation mechanisms have emerged as a key strategy to resolve such conflicts. These financial instruments aim to align ecological and economic interests, as demonstrated by large-scale initiatives like the pilot program in China's Xin'an River Basin (XARB). There, a top-down, government-funded approach successfully improved water quality through significant investment in pollution control and restoration (Ren et al., 2020). While effective in that context, such a model, reliant on substantial central funding, may not be directly transferable to contexts like community-managed wetlands in Nepal, where financial resources are scarcer and local participation is paramount for long-term sustainability.

This gap underscores the need for alternative, bottom-up approaches to conservation financing. Therefore, this study focuses on Jhakhori Lake to investigate a community-based perspective by assessing residents' willingness to pay (WTP) for wetland conservation. The primary objectives are to: (1) estimate the mean WTP to establish a foundational economic value for the lake's ecosystem services, (2) identify the key socioeconomic and attitudinal factors that determine WTP, and (3) provide evidence-based recommendations for designing locally acceptable and financially viable conservation strategies. By quantifying the value residents place on their natural heritage, this research aims to contribute to the development of democratically informed and sustainable management policies for Jhakhori Lake and similar wetlands in Nepal.

Study Method

Contingent valuation method

This study employed the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) to estimate the economic value residents place on the conservation of Jhakhor Lake. As a stated-preference technique, CVM is uniquely suited for valuing non-market environmental goods by constructing a hypothetical market scenario and directly asking individuals about their Willingness to Pay (WTP) (Upadhyay, 2022; Upadhyay et al. 2025). This approach is grounded in the principle of utility maximization, where respondents' choices reveal the value they assign to a change in the provision of an environmental good (Thapa et al., 2022). To elicit WTP, a detailed hypothetical scenario was presented to respondents, describing the current threats to Jhakhor Lake and a proposed conservation program to ensure its long-term health. The WTP metric was selected as it provides a direct, democratic basis for establishing a credible conservation fund or eco-compensation standard reflective of local preferences (Ren et al., 2020). A critical concern in CVM studies is potential bias. To enhance the reliability and validity of the estimates, this study implemented several mitigation strategies. The WTP was elicited using an iterative bidding game technique. This method, which reduces starting point bias by progressively adjusting the bid amount based on a respondent's previous answer, is recognized for improving response quality despite being more time-consuming Davis, 1963; cited in (Nirere, 2012). Furthermore, the survey instrument was carefully designed based on a review of common biases (Lamsal et al., 2015), and included a detailed information section to ensure participants were well-informed before stating their WTP. Based on the approaches of (Asmamaw et al., 2016; Dos Reis et al., 2022), the mean WTP for the sampled population was calculated as follows:

$$E(WTP) = \sum_{i=1}^n b_i \times P_i \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where: **WTP** is the expected value of the mean willingness to pay. **P_i** represents the *i*th payment amount presented to respondents. **b_i** denotes the proportion of respondents who accepted the *i*th bid value. And n is the number of samples.

Econometric Model

Identifying the socioeconomic determinants of residents' Willingness to Pay (WTP) is crucial, as it not only validates the reliability of the WTP estimates but also provides policymakers with empirical evidence to design targeted conservation strategies (Adhikari et al., 2017). A common challenge in WTP surveys is the presence of zero responses, where participants state an unwillingness to pay. Using standard regression techniques like Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) or Probit models to analyze such data can yield biased and inconsistent parameter estimates, as these methods do not adequately account for the censored nature of the dependent variable (Upadhyay, 2022). The Tobit model, a censored regression model, is specifically designed for situations where the dependent variable is continuous for positive values but clustered at zero (Chu et al., 2020; Upadhyay et al. 2025) This makes it a more robust and appropriate estimator for analyzing WTP data containing zero responses. Therefore, this study employs the Tobit model to identify the factors influencing residents' WTP for the conservation of Jhakhor Lake. Following the approach of (Austin et al., 2018), the general form of the Tobit model is specified as follows::

$$Y^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i + \mu, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

and $\mu \sim (0, \sigma^2)$

$$\begin{aligned} y_i &= y^* && \text{if } y_i^* > 0 \\ y_i &= 0 && \text{if } y_i^* \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where Y^* denote a latent variable, y_i is dependent variable, X_i is an explanatory variable, β_0 is a solve parameter, and μ refers to stochastic error.

Building on the determinants identified in prior contingent valuation studies (Maskey & Singh, 2017), the

explanatory variables for this analysis were categorized into three key dimensions: (1) residents' socio-demographic characteristics, (2) household economic features, and (3) their awareness and perceptions of wetland conservation. The standard Tobit model was then used to estimate the conditional expected value of WTP (Oduor et al., 2018), specified as follows:

$$\text{Max_WTP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \dots + \beta_nX_n + \mu_i \quad (4)$$

where: WTP denotes the amount that residents are willing to pay for wetland conservation, β_0 is the constant term (intercept), $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ are the regression coefficients to be estimated, X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n represent the explanatory variables (socio-demographic, economic, and attitudinal factors), μ is the stochastic error term, assumed to be independently and normally distributed with a mean of zero.

Data collection

Primary data were collected through a cross-sectional survey of 411 local residents at Jhakhor Lake between January 25 and February 20, 2025. The research design was informed by two preliminary focus group discussions with local stakeholders, which provided critical insights for questionnaire development. Sampling employed a simple random approach, explicitly including permanent residents and resource-dependent users to maintain focus on tourism perspectives (Upadhyay et al. 2025). The survey achieved a 100% response rate through face-to-face interviews.

The structured questionnaire, translated into Nepali and Tharu language and pre-tested for cultural appropriateness, followed established environmental valuation frameworks (Ren et al., 2020). It contained four sections: (1) research context and wetland scenarios; (2) conservation awareness assessment; (3) WTP elicitation using a payment card (NPR 0-1000) following contingent valuation standards (Ren et al., 2020) and (4) socioeconomic profile.

In this study, a total of 411 local residents aged 20 years and above from the Jhakhor Lake area were selected as respondents. The survey primarily focused on two issues: the extent of public awareness regarding wetland conservation initiatives and their level of satisfaction with the current conservation efforts in the lake. Additionally, respondents were asked a willingness-to-pay (WTP) question framed as follows: "If you directly benefit from the ecological improvements in Jhakhor Lake, how much would you be willing to contribute for its conservation?" Upadhyay et al. (2025) stated that the payment options provided ranged from 0 to 100 Nepalese Rupees (25, 50, 75, and 100). These bid values were determined based on a pilot survey conducted prior to the main data collection to ensure their appropriateness and reliability.

Trained enumerators administered the survey following standardized protocols. Key metrics included visitation patterns, conservation attitudes, and maximum WTP for lake conservation (Upadhyay, 2022). Data analysis utilized descriptive statistics and Tobit regression to identify WTP determinants. This methodology ensures robust valuation of conservation preferences while maintaining methodological rigor appropriate for policy-relevant ecological economics research.

Results and Discussions

Main characteristics of residents

Table 1 presents the socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of the respondents. Out of the total sample, 63.26% were male and 36.74% female. The majority of respondents (57.91%) belonged to the 26–45 age group, followed by 26.52% in the 46–60 group. More than half (53.53%) had no formal education,

while only 10.95% had attained a bachelor's degree or above. In terms of occupation, most respondents (86.37%) were self-employed, and only 13.63% were government workers. Income distribution shows that 40.15% earned $\leq 10,000$ NPR per month, while a small proportion (7.30%) reported earnings above 40,000 NPR. Regarding residential proximity to the lake, 29.20% lived within 4 km, 24.33% within 1 km, and fewer (9.49%) within 3 km. When asked about the responsible body for wetland conservation, the largest share (34.31%) identified local people, followed by the Nepal Government (25.30%) and NGOs/INGOs (20.19%). Perceptions of government performance in conservation were mixed: 71.53% rated it as poor, 24.09% as good, and only 4.38% as very good.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the residents

Variable	Index	frequency	%
Gender	Male	151	36.74
	Female	260	63.26
Age	20–25	34	8.27
	26–45	238	57.91
	46–60	109	26.52
	>60	30	7.30
Education	No-formal education	220	53.53
	Up to Secondary level	146	35.52
	Bachelor Degree and above	45	10.95
Occupation	Government worker	56	13.63
	Self-employed	355	86.37
Income	$\leq 10,000$	165	40.15
	10,001–20,000	139	33.82
	20,001–30,000	67	16.30
	30,001–40,000	10	2.43
	>40,000	30	7.30
Distance	1 KM	100	24.33
	2KM	68	16.55
	3KM	39	9.49
	4KM	120	29.20
	5KM	84	20.44
Responsible Body	Nepal Government	104	25.30
	Local People	141	34.31
	NGOs / INGOs	83	20.19
	Tourists	83	20.19
Government Role	Poor	294	71.53
	Good	99	24.09
	Very Good	18	4.38

Source: Authors' compilation based on field survey

Statistical Analysis of Residents' Awareness of Wetland Conservation

Residents' perceptions of wetland conservation in Jhakhor Lake are presented in Figure 2. The results show that the majority of respondents (46.47%) attached the greatest value to the lake as an asset to be preserved for future generations. About 19.22% emphasized its recreational importance, while 16.55% highlighted its role as a direct source of income. In addition, 17.76% of respondents valued the very existence of the lake, recognizing its ecological and cultural significance. These findings suggest that in the context of a developing country like Nepal, conservation of natural resources such as Jhakhor Lake is not only viewed through an economic lens but also strongly associated with intergenerational responsibility and ecological sustainability.

Figure 2. *Perceived value*

The assessment of residents' awareness and perceptions of wetland conservation at Jhakhor Lake reveals a varied picture across different dimensions. With regard to understanding, many residents fell between relatively low (31.4%) and relatively high (23.9%) levels of awareness, while about one-fifth (20.3%) demonstrated very high understanding. Encouragingly, support for conservation measures was quite strong, with more than half of the respondents (55.0%) showing relatively high or very high support, and fewer than one-third (27.8%) expressing low support. However, when asked to prioritize environmental protection over economic development, opinions were more divided. Nearly one-third (28.0%) remained neutral, and over two-fifths (41.6%) placed greater emphasis on economic concerns. Satisfaction with ongoing conservation initiatives emerged as the weakest area: only about one-third (33.8%) of respondents reported being satisfied, whereas nearly half (46.8%) indicated dissatisfaction. Overall, these findings highlight that while awareness and support for wetland conservation are fairly strong, limited satisfaction and the tension between environmental and economic priorities present challenges for the long-term success of conservation efforts.

Figure 3. Environmental Awareness

Willingness to pay for the protection of Jakhor Taal

As shown in the frequency distribution, 371 residents were willing to pay positive amounts (WTP > 0), accounting for 90.27% of the total sample of 411 respondents. However, there were notable variations in their willingness to pay amounts, which were discretely distributed across several bid points.

The WTP values showed a concentration pattern around specific bid amounts. The most frequent willingness to pay was 25 NPR, with 137 residents (33.33% of respondents) selecting this amount. This was followed by 50 NPR (25.55%) and 75 NPR (17.76%), indicating that the majority of residents' WTP was concentrated in the lower to medium range of the bid amounts offered. Only 56 residents (13.63%) were willing to pay the highest amount of 100 NPR, while 40 residents (9.73%) reported zero willingness to pay for wetland conservation. The distribution suggests that while there is substantial support for wetland conservation among Jhakhor Lake residents, the acceptable payment levels tend to cluster at more modest amounts, possibly reflecting the local economic conditions and income levels in the region.

Table 2. Willingness to pay (WTPi)

Initial bids	Frequency	Percent
0	40	9.73
25	137	33.33
50	105	25.55
75	73	17.76
100	56	13.63

Our contingent valuation survey revealed strong public support for wetland conservation at Jhakhor Lake. Of the 411 households surveyed, 371 respondents (90.27%) expressed positive willingness to pay (WTP) for conservation initiatives, while 40 households (9.73%) reported zero WTP, indicating broad-based community endorsement for preservation efforts. The distribution of WTP values exhibited substantial heterogeneity and

pronounced right-skewness (Skewness = 7.10, Shapiro-Wilk $W = 0.388$, $p < 0.001$). The median WTP stood at 120 NPR annually, while the mean WTP was 249.20 NPR (SD = 455.30), with values ranging from 0 to 5,100 NPR. The significant disparity between median and mean values, coupled with high kurtosis (69.15), indicates that the distribution is heavily influenced by a small proportion of high-WTP respondents.

Key factors influencing the willingness to pay

Table 4 presents the determinants of willingness to pay for wetland conservation using both OLS and Tobit specifications. The models demonstrate strong explanatory power, with key socioeconomic and behavioral factors emerging as significant predictors.

Educational attainment exhibits a strong positive association with WTP, with secondary-educated respondents demonstrating higher valuation ($\beta=1.111$, $p<0.01$) than bachelor-level counterparts. Income elasticity is positive and significant ($\beta=0.615$, $p<0.01$), confirming economic capacity as a key determinant. Behavioral factors reveal striking patterns: frequent visitors to Jhakhor Lake show substantially higher WTP ($\beta=3.175$, $p<0.01$), while increasing distance from the wetland significantly reduces valuation ($\beta=-0.429$, $p<0.01$), emphasizing use value's importance.

Notably, larger household sizes correlate with reduced WTP, suggesting budget constraint effects. The Tobit model's significant sigma parameter (1.150, $p<0.01$) confirms the censored nature of WTP data, validating our empirical approach. Overall, results highlight that both economic capacity (income, education) and behavioral engagement (visitation frequency, proximity) drive conservation valuation, with implications for targeted conservation financing strategies.

Table 3. OLS and Tobit regression results

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)
Dependent var. ln (Max WTP)	OLS	Tobit
Age	0.0111** (0.00462)	0.0140** (0.00564)
Edu Secondary level	1.009*** (0.117)	1.111*** (0.151)
Edu Bachelor and above	0.613*** (0.209)	0.678*** (0.257)
Job Opportunity	0.368** (0.158)	0.324** (0.141)
Hhsize	-0.991*** (0.195)	-1.000*** (0.159)
Income	0.584** (0.251)	0.615*** (0.200)
Distance	-0.400*** (0.0374)	-0.429*** (0.0488)
Visit frequently	2.489*** (0.214)	3.175*** (0.420)
Value reserving for future	-0.214* (0.112)	-0.234* (0.125)
Constant	3.334***	2.645***

	(0.424)	(0.578)
Sigma	-	1.150***
	-	(0.0592)
Observations	411	411
R-squared	0.651	0.256

*, **, and *** denote significance at 10%, 5%, and 1%, respectively.

This study provides among the first empirical evidence of residents' willingness to pay (WTP) for wetland conservation in Nepal, addressing a critical research gap in the economic valuation of Himalayan aquatic ecosystems. Our findings demonstrate that household WTP is significantly influenced by socioeconomic characteristics and Geographic factors, with education, income, and proximity to Jhakhor Lake emerging as key determinants. These results align with contingent valuation studies globally, yet reveal context-specific patterns relevant to developing mountain economies.

The positive association between educational attainment and WTP underscores the role of environmental awareness in conservation support, while the income elasticity reflects economic capacity constraints typical of rural economies. Crucially, the strong distance decay effect whereby proximity to the wetland increases WTP highlights the importance of use values in driving conservation preferences. This spatial heterogeneity mirrors findings from river basin studies in China (Fanus et al., 2016) but contrasts with contexts where government-led initiatives homogenize preferences (He et al., 2015).

Methodologically, our treatment of zero WTP responses follows (Adhikari et al. 2017) approach, maintaining sample representativeness while acknowledging potential conservative valuation. The resulting estimates likely represent lower-bound values, as they exclude institutional stakeholders. Nevertheless, the aggregate economic value demonstrates substantial community-level support for conservation, suggesting potential for locally-financed conservation initiatives alongside government interventions.

These findings carry important policy implications for Nepal's wetland management, indicating that conservation strategies should account for socioeconomic heterogeneity and spatial targeting to enhance effectiveness and equity in ecosystem service provision.

Conclusion

This study provides a critical assessment of residents' willingness to pay (WTP) for wetland conservation in Jhakhor Lake, Nepal, employing contingent valuation methodology to address persistent gaps in the economic valuation of Himalayan aquatic ecosystems. Our findings demonstrate substantial community support for conservation, with 90.27% of respondents expressing positive WTP highlighting the significant value residents place on wetland ecosystem services.

The analysis reveals considerable spatial and socioeconomic heterogeneity in conservation preferences. Key determinants including education ($\beta=1.111$, $p<0.01$), income ($\beta=0.615$, $p<0.01$), and particularly distance to the wetland ($\beta=-0.429$, $p<0.01$) emerge as powerful predictors of WTP, underscoring the complex interplay between economic capacity, environmental awareness, and spatial factors in shaping conservation preferences. The significant distance-decay effect emphasizes the localized nature of wetland benefits and the importance of incorporating spatial dimensions in environmental valuation.

The findings of this study offer actionable insights for wetland conservation policy in Nepal and similar contexts. The significant socioeconomic and spatial variation in WTP underscores the need for differentiated conservation finance mechanisms, such as tiered payment structures that reflect both ability-to-pay and benefit-received principles. Furthermore, spatially-targeted interventions are recommended, where conservation programs prioritize outreach and education for distant households while leveraging the strong support from proximate communities. The substantial aggregate WTP demonstrated by households provides a compelling foundation for integrated financing, suggesting that community contributions can and should be blended with national and international conservation funds to ensure sustainable management.

This research, however, is not without its limitations. The cross-sectional design captures stated preferences at a single point in time, and longitudinal tracking is needed to understand preference dynamics. The focus on household perspectives also excludes other critical stakeholders, such as agricultural users, local businesses, and downstream communities. Future research should therefore incorporate spatial econometrics to model spillover effects and employ choice experiments to better understand the trade-offs residents are willing to make between different conservation attributes.

Notwithstanding these limitations, this study establishes a critical benchmark for the economic valuation of Himalayan wetlands and demonstrates the clear viability of community-supported conservation financing in Nepal. As these ecosystems face escalating threats from climate change and development pressures, understanding the economic value communities place on their preservation is increasingly urgent. By quantifying this support and identifying its key determinants, this research provides policymakers with the empirical evidence needed to design more effective, equitable, and sustainable conservation strategies that are firmly aligned with local preferences and regional environmental objectives.

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